

BB-2208 Human Resource Management

Lecturer: Pg Dr Siti Rozaidah binti Pg Hj Idris

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT 2

Case Study Analysis
Agrowmetro Company: Standard Causal Model of HRM

Prepared by:

REG.NO	STUDENT NAME
17b1010	Iffah Haziyah @ Hanna Ainina Binti Rumaizi

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Executive Summary

This report provides an evaluation of the issues that prevails within Agrometro Company using the Standard Causal Model of HRM. This report draws attention to the two main issues; the lack of finance and the insufficient human resources. The former may be caused by a lack of finance manager in the company hence resulting in poor utilisation of the funds and the latter issue goes back to the lack of finance, hence causing the inability to hire more labours. Upon further analysis of these issues, it is difficult to apply the theory of the Standard Causal Model of HRM within the company as the HR chains in the model requires one of the key resource for any organisation; the employees. Though, it is still possible for the company to experience positive HR outcome from implementing HR strategy with the current employees, but the impact to the overall operation of the company may not be enough due to the lack in staff. Therefore to counter these problems, one of the solution is to hire a finance manager to improve the management of the firm's fund. The other solution is for the firm to offer internship programmes which is less costly for the firm. Further findings conclude that the former solution may be the most optimum to solve the issues within the company.

Problem Statement

There are two main issues that Agrowmetro faces:

- *The lack of finance.*

Agrowmetro company has been operating since 2017 and they have been receiving positive demand and support from the market for their hydroponic systems (Musa, Pg Hj Idris and Basir, 2020). Assuming this company might still struggle financially and the pattern of demand for their hydroponic systems has remained encouraging to this day, the reason why this issue may persist is the unavailability of a financial manager to keep track of their finance efficiently.

- *Insufficient human resources.*

The company is run by four people which comprises only the director, resident seedling expert, marketing manager and head manager. It is acknowledged that the lack of employees to help Agrowmetro operate efficiently goes back to the lack of finance, hence has brought in this issue.

The Standard Causal model of HRM is a causal chain model that begins with the overall business strategy and ends with the improved internal and financial performance which is achieved through the Human Resource processes (Vulpen, 2019). Hence, this model illustrates that when the overall organizational strategy is aligning with the Human Resource processes, it can lead to an improvement to the overall performance of the organization which includes improved internal performance and financial stability. However, the application of the theory of the Standard Causal Model may be difficult for Agrowmetry Company due to the lack of employees available in the company.

The Standard Causal Model of HRM

Source: ResearchGate.net

Case Analysis (516 words)

In order to apply the Standard Causal Model of HRM into the administration aspects of Agrowmetro Company, it can be analyzed step-by-step from the beginning to the end of the chain:

- *Overall Strategy.*

So far, the known business strategies are the sale of hydroponic systems at the farmer's market and the use of social media like Instagram to advertise the products. Hence, the basic plan of action of the company was selling the products at a strategic time (during the *Hari Peladang dan Ternakan*) and marketing the products to better reach the audience that have high interest in their products which are the farming enthusiasts. It can be assumed that one of the company's basic objectives is to make profit from selling the hydroponic systems.

- *HR strategy and HR practice.*

This includes "hiring, training, appraisal and compensation" (Vulpen, 2019). Since the Agrowmetro company only comprises four employees, it may be difficult but still possible to apply the basic HR strategies among themselves, however, the result from such implementations of HR strategies could be better with more employees. Since they are lacking employees, one of the solutions for this issue includes recruiting interns, which will be elaborated in the next section.

An example of an HR practice is the application of reward management system. The manager of Agrowmetro Company can recompense the employees with extrinsic rewards (e.g bonuses and recognition). Many organisations have relied on this as their main method to increase employees' motivation (Franco-Santos and Gomez-Mejia, 2015). Meanwhile, the intrinsic rewards can be referred to four variables; sense of purpose, sense of choice, sense of maturity in their skills and sense of belonging in a group (Thomas and Velthouse, 1990; Deci &

Ryan,2002).When employees are experiencing these positive emotions, it means that their job is intrinsically rewarding (Franco-Santos and Gomez-Mejia, 2015).

- *HR outcomes.*

This chain refers to the results from the implementation of the HR strategy and practice. From the previous example, the main expected outcome from the implementation of the reward management system is increased employees' motivation.

Other outcomes from implementing any HR bundles include high commitment, satisfaction and loyalty (Boselie, Dietz and Boon, 2005).

- *Improved internal performance and financial performance.*

The HR outcome it will also result in improved internal performance, such as enhanced employee productivity, innovation and higher quality of work. This in turn leads to improvement of the financial performance. For example, higher profits, better results in the company's asset turnover, inventory turnover and so on.

- *The unmediated HRM effect and reversed causality.*

Some HR practices could directly cause an enhancement in the internal performance of the organisation, thus causing an unmediated HRM effect. For example, if employees of Agrowmetro receives better training in assembling the hydroponics system, this will lead to better output of their work without influencing the HR outcome.

The reversed causality occurs when the company is experiencing a stable financial performance, it could lead to investments towards the HR practices which will lead to HR outcomes. The lack of finance is one of Agrowmetro's main issue which is linked with the lack of employees working for the company.

Solutions

- *Improving financial performance through financial management.*

This solution attempts to counter the lack of finance available which slows down the potential growth of Agrowmetro Company. (Paramasivan and Subramanian, n.d) explained that financial management is considered to be the most essential part in the scope of business, especially in the current era of innovation in the field of commerce. The authors explained that financial management defined by S.C Kuchal is “ *the dealings with procurement of funds and their effective utilisation in the business*”. This falls as a duty to the financial managers in the firm (which is currently not available in Agrowmetro company). Moreover, the objectives of the financial managers are profit maximisation and wealth maximisation which helps firms to gain more profit and improve the value of shareholders (respectively).

Applying this theory in the context of Agrowmetro company, they can consider hiring a financial manager to help assist their business operation. Since they are experiencing encouraging demand for their hydroponics system since 2017, it is assumed that they have a relatively stable profit gain. Hence, the profit can be managed more effectively to aid the growth of the company, which includes being able to afford to hire more employees perhaps starting with hiring a financial manager. However due to their current financial constraint which could limit this initiative, the company can consider hiring a qualified financial manager from the i-Ready Apprenticeship Programme that was introduced by the government in April 2017 (Hj Abu Bakar, 2019). After they hire a financial manager that helps the improvement in the aspect of financial management, the company can hire more employees to fill up the other departments. Going back to the Standard Causal Model of HRM, this solution could cause a reversed causality where the improved financial performance leads to more investments in HR strategy and results in HR outcome.

- *Opening an internship program*

The next issue of the company is the insufficient human resource which can also be solved with the application of the previous solution. Another solution to counter this issue is opening an internship program. This can be done by offering internship openings to higher education institutions to earn extra credits or the general public for the sake of learning the skills which may appeal to the farming enthusiasts.

According to (Galloway, Marks and Chillias, 2013), interns are considered to be a less costly source of labours. The interns can be utilised to carry on value added projects which otherwise might not be able to be accomplished by the company (Maertz et al, 2014).

Moreover, another benefit of employing interns when their internship period is over, is that it could help reduce the costs of recruitment and training (Holyoak, 2013). The period of internship can be considered as a trial period for the company as the employer and the student as the potential employee (Elarde & Chong, 2012).

(Volsoban, 2012) explained that it is highly important for firms to know how to manage and invest in their resources to employ more labours. The author explained that the extent of the firm's competitiveness will also depend on the company's performance management on their employees. Furthermore, when these employees are able to produce high performance it can result in success and brings excellent image to the company. In the context of the Standard Causal Model of HRM, this solution may help the company have more employees hence results in a greater impact from the implementation of the HR strategy which aligns with the overall strategy of the business.

However, one drawback from opening the internship program is that it is merely a temporary solution, hence the interns' performance contributed to the company is limited due to the time

constraint of their internship period. Moreover, after the interns are done with the program there is no guarantee that these interns are able to be recruited as employees.

Recommendation

The optimum solution for the main issues.

Agrowmetro company should aim for a proper financial function within their administration. It is possible that root of the problem is the insufficient management of the profit which contributes to the lack of finance and human resource. Hence, possible optimum solution is the improvement of the financial performance through financial management.

Linking this back to the Standard Causal Model of HRM, a reversed causality effect could happen when the company make investments by hiring more employees, combined with the implementation with the HR strategy whilst aligning with the overall strategy of the business.

Hiring a financial manager and their functions for the firm

(Paramasivan and Subramanian, n.d) further highlighted the important functions of a financial manager. Finance is considered as a significant component in the fixed and ongoing processes of the company's business aspect. This is due to the fact that finance is interrelated with the other functions of the firm such as the marketing department, the production function and the human resource. The issue of the financial aspect is commonly focused by many businesses as it is an important component that reflects the firm's stance in terms of its ability to operate and profitability.

A financial manager is different from an accountant, because he would have various knowledge from different fields, such as accounting, management, finance and economics (Paramasivan and Subramanian, n.d). Hence, the financial manager will have one of the most important role in the firm as this job requires the ability to be evaluative and methodical in any circumstances where financial issues may arise. The author explained the following major functions of the financial manager:

1) Foresee the financial requirements

This is considered to be the primary role of the financial manager. He is expected to do various estimations on important financial decisions for the company, such as how much finance is needed to obtain fixed assets and forecast how much investment is required to qualify for the needed working capital in the future.

2) Purchasing important capital

After finalising the required amount of finance, the next function is deciding the mobility the fund and have the ability to know where can the fund be obtained.

3) Making investment decisions

The finance manager also have to scrutinise the best selection of investment alternatives that could bring the most substantial return.

4) *Cash management*

The present days cash is also essential to have proper management. Other than for the sake of effective utilisation of those funds, it can also help to meet short-term liquidity.

5) *Link to other departments*

Finance deals with all the important departments in the firm, such as marketing, research and development, system and human resource. Hence, the finance manager should not limit his knowledge in only finance aspects, but also well versed on other areas as well. Therefore, it is important for the finance manager to maintain a good relationship with all the other departments.

The significance of financial management

(Paramasivan and Subramanian, n.d) considered finance as the life force of any organisations. For any issues that arises within the firm, there has to be a sufficient amount of fund to ensure there is smooth operation of the business to achieve their objectives. The author further explained the significance of financial management:

1) *Financial planning*

Without proper financial planning, it will be difficult for firms to flourish in the ever competitive business world.

2) *The derivation of funds*

Obtaining the needed funds for the firm is important in financial management and the optimum way is to obtain them at a minimum cost.

3) *The appropriate utilisation of funds*

With proper utilisation of the finance, it will increase the firm's operational efficiency because it will reduce the cost of capital whilst raising the value of the business.

4) *Aids the firm's decision making process*

Finance has a direct impact on the critical departments of the firm, hence it is wise for the firm to make careful financial decisions.

5) *Increase the firm's profitability*

However, this depends on how efficient is the utilisation of the firm's fund. With the use of financial control mechanisms like the ratio analysis, this could help raise the firm's profitability.

6) Raised value of firm and encouraging savings

Value refers to the wealth of investors and financial management can help raising this aspect. The objectives of any businesses is to accomplish profit maximisation which simultaneously raise the investors' wealth. Meanwhile, savings can only occur when the firm is able to achieve both profit and wealth maximisation.

In the context of Agrometro Company, having a proper financial management is significant to achieve any of their business objectives and it could even help them making their mission to revolutionise the farming technology in Brunei come into reality. Therefore, hiring a finance manager is considered as an investment for the company that could help the company utilise the profits from selling the hydroponics system and use those funds for further expansion.

Conclusion

The theory of the Standard Causal Model can be applied within Agrometro Company when the firm has the ability to hire more employees to implement HR strategies that aligns with the firm's overall strategy in order to bring improvement to the internal and financial performance. This can be done through hiring a finance manager to oversee the utilisation of the funds to ensure there is growth of the business. This solution is chosen to be the optimum choice, because the intership programme may be able to help to resolve the issues but only temporarily due to the time constraint of the period of intership.

Financial management is considered to be the heart any organisation because finance is interrelated with the other critical departments of the firm. Therefore, with the proper management of funds within Agrometro Company it can serve as a permanent solution for any other issues that may arise.

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